

Design and Testing of Nanotechnology Based Sequential Circuits Using MX-CQCA Logic in VHDL

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Abstract : This paper provides the design of two vectors testable sequential circuits based on multiplexer conservative QCA (MX-CQCA) logic gates. The proposed sequential circuits based on conservative logic gates smash the sequential circuits implemented in traditional gates in terms of testability. Reversible circuits are similar to conventional logic circuits except that they are built from reversible gates. In reversible gates, there is a unique, one-to-one mapping between the inputs and outputs, not the case with conventional logic. The designs of two vectors testable latches, master-slave flip-flops and double edge triggered (DET) flip-flops in VLSI design are also presented. The objective behind the proposed design methodologies is to amalgamate arithmetic and logic functional units optimizing key metrics such as garbage outputs, quantum cost and delay. The proposed MX-CQCA gate outshines the other reversible gate in terms of the intricacy (the number of majority voters), speed and area.

Keywords : Quantum dot Cellular automata, conservative logic, MX-CQCA gate, reversible logic, Double edge triggered (DET) flip flop.

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